

CGFI Outputs Directory

This document is intended to signpost archived or external outputs previously hosted on the UK Centre for Greening Finance and Investment (UK CGFI) website. This is not an exhaustive list of CGFI outputs and activities. For more information please see our [Legacy page](#).

Wind/flood risk to infrastructure

- Tool [Wind/Flood Risk Correlation Explorer](#)
- Paper [Co-occurring wintertime flooding and extreme wind over Europe, from daily to seasonal timescales](#)
- Paper [Synoptic conditions conducive for compound wind-flood events in Great Britain in present and future climates](#)
- Paper [Open-access R code for translating the co-occurrence of natural hazards into impact on joint financial risk](#)
- Paper [Increasingly Seasonal Jet Stream Raises Risk of Co-Occurring Flooding and Extreme Wind in Great Britain](#)
- Event [Workshop: Compound Wind and Flood events collaborative Workshop](#)
- Case study [Visualising wind and flood hazards in Europe](#)
- Blog [What if it's a perfect storm? Stronger evidence that insurers should account for co-occurring weather hazards](#)

Tropical Cyclone Risk

- Paper [The Imperial College Storm Model \(IRIS\) Dataset](#)
- Case study [IRIS and Attribution Science](#)
- Tool [IriS Imperial College Storm Model \(Github\)](#)

Infrastructure risks (Resilient Planet Data Hub)

- Tool [Tool: GRI Risk Viewer](#)
- Initiative [Initiative: Resilient Planet Data Hub](#)
- Discussion paper [Discussion Paper: Aligning Finance with Climate-Resilient Development](#)
- Metrics and report [Aligning Finance with Adaptation and Resilience Goals – Targets and Metrics for Financial Institutions \(superseded by 2024 update\)](#)
- Report [Towards a Climate Risk Data Architecture: Common and Open Risk Metrics](#)
- Report [Assessing Financial Risks from Physical Climate Shocks: A Framework for Scenario Generation](#)
- Report [Report: Managing Risk in a More Complex World](#)
- Working paper [Climate-resilient Finance and Investment: Framing Paper](#)
- Report [Mobilizing Finance for Adaptation at COP27: Next Steps in Aligning Finance and Investment with Climate-Resilient Development Goals](#)
- Paper [Acute climate risks in the financial system: examining the utility of climate model projections](#)
- Blog [Enabling Data-Driven Investment in Adaptation and Nature: Introducing the Resilient Planet Data Hub](#)
- Podcast [Balancing Mitigation and Adaptation: Insights for the Financial Sector](#)
- Blog [To mobilise the trillions needed for climate adaptation, the world needs a common language of risk](#)
- Event [EGU General Assembly 2024: Physical climate risk, sovereign credit ratings, and the benefits of adaptation](#)
- Case study [Scenario analysis to understand climate financial risk in South East Asia](#)
- Case study [Mobilising investments into resilient infrastructure in East Africa.](#)

Transition risk and transition planning

- Working paper [Working paper: An input-output sensitivity analysis of climate-economy integrated assessment](#)
- Blog [Blog: Credible firm-level transition plans need credible national actions](#)

Discussion paper	Toward A Framework For Assessing And Using Current Climate Risk Scenarios Within Financial Decisions
Working paper	Climate Transition Plans' Assessment in Hard-to-Abate Sectors: Evidence from Airlines
Working paper	Assessing Corporate Emissions Reduction Targets Against National Transition Plans
Working paper	Impact of climate scenario choices on climate financial risk assessment: High variance company performance under consistent climate stress test
Working paper	Assessing Corporate Transition Plans using a Production Asset-Based Planning Approach
Working paper	Corporate net zero transition and financing cost: Evidence of impact from global energy and utilities sectors
Working paper	Sustainability-Linked Bonds: Modelling for Sustainability Performance
Working paper	A framework for assessing and managing dependencies in corporate transition plans
Working paper	Enhancing Comparability and Credibility of Transition Plans and Transition Risk Assessment with Standardized Net Zero Scenarios
Discussion paper	Emission and Technology Pathways in the Shipping Sector
Working paper	Assessing Corporate Transition Plans using a Production Asset-Based Planning Approach
Discussion paper	Data Quality Considerations for Estimating Financed Emissions
Discussion paper	A sectoral approach to tackling sustainability data quality and integrity in sustainable finance
Initiative	Transition Plan Taskforce – see here for all TPT-related outputs
Podcast	A Climate Pledge Without A Plan Is A Wish

CBES project

Report	Report: CBES recommendations report (CGFI)
Report	Report: CBES survey report (CGFI and UK CFRF)
Report	Report: CBES insurance workshop report
Report	CBES banking workshop report
Event	What comes next after CBES, and what role for integrated climate-nature risk analysis?

Spatial Finance Initiative

Report	Location Location Location: Asset-Location Data Sources for Nature-related Financial Risk Analysis
Report	State and Trends of Spatial Finance 2023
Report	State and Trends of Spatial Finance 2021
Paper	A Field-Level Asset Mapping Dataset for England's Agricultural Sector
Paper	Location, location, location: asset location data sources for nature-related financial risk analysis
Paper	Breaking the ESG rating divergence: An open geospatial framework for environmental scores
Paper	Global database of cement production assets and upstream suppliers
Paper	Spatial finance: practical and theoretical contributions to financial analysis
Paper	A global inventory of photovoltaic solar energy generating units
Report	Climate Risk Analysis from Space
Dataset	Beef Abattoir Database (Top 5 Meatpackers) (archive copy)
Dataset	Global Database of Cement Production Assets (archive copy)
Dataset	Global Database of Iron and Steel Production Assets (archive copy)
Dataset	Global Ethylene Production Database (archive copy)
Dataset	Global Pulp and Paper Mill Database (archive copy)
Dataset	Municipal Wastewater Treatment Plant Database for Europe (archive copy)
Podcast	Geospatial Data, Climate Risk and Financial-Decisionmaking in Spatial Finance – Climind
Event	Spatial Finance Initiative Launch Event

Additional Associate Fellow collaborations

Discussion paper	A Climate Scenario Taxonomy for the Financial Sector
Discussion paper	The Challenge of Climate Risk Modelling in Financial Institutions – Overview, Critique and Guidance
Tool	Network Reevaluation Model

Leeds Innovation Hub

- Event [Collaborating for Impact: Bridging the gap between climate science and insurance industry practice](#)
- Event [Communicating with Customers on Physical Climate Risk: Barriers, Motivations and Opportunities for Action](#)
- Event [Collaboration for Impact: Exploration and Advancement of Climate Risk Analytics for the Building Society Sector](#)
- Event [Collaborating for impact: bridging the gap between climate science and insurance industry practice](#)
- Event [Research Theme Update for the Insurance Sector](#)
- Event [Collaborating for impact: climate science and insurance industry practice – research theme update](#)
- Initiative [CGFI internships](#)
- Event [CGFI Hackathon 2025 – Global characteristics of tropical cyclones: tropical risk analytics for the reinsurance industry – key takeaways](#)
- Initiative [Leeds Innovation Hub](#)
- Event [Workshop: From research to application in the insurance industry](#)

London Innovation Hub & Innovation activities

- Report + Event [Green Fintech 2.0: Next Generation Climate and Environmental Analytics to Accelerate Green Finance](#)
- Blog [Green and nature fintech – takeaways from our expert panels](#)
- Blog [Reckoning with a just coal transition](#)
- Blog [Green Fintech for Green Finance: Turning Theory into Practice](#)
- Event [London Innovation Hub Launch](#)
- Initiative [Data Analytics Prize \(Climate Investment Challenge\)](#)
- Initiative [The Greenhouse \(Climate/Green Fintech strand\)](#)
- Podcast [Fintech Scotland podcast](#)
- Event [CGFI Connect – Insurance and Climate Science: Bringing Together Research and Practice](#)

Additional events, engagement and knowledge exchange

- Event [CGFI Annual Forum 2024](#)
- Event [CGFI Annual Forum 2023](#)
- Event [CGFI Annual Forum 2022](#)
- Blog [3 takeaways for researchers from a year at a pension fund](#)
- Publications [Who pays? Money, power and risk in sustainable finance](#)
- Publications [Harnessing climate data \(UBS x Nest x University of Oxford\)](#)
- Initiative [UK Climate Financial Risk Forum](#)